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D4.2 - Natural hydrogen in the national energy laws – overview of possibilities

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Summary

This report analyses the legal and institutional frameworks for natural hydrogen in four HyAfrica countries—South Africa, Morocco, Mozambique, and Togo—and proposes strategies to address key regulatory gaps. Drawing from international benchmarks (Australia, Colombia, France, and Poland), it finds that most countries regulate natural hydrogen through existing mining or energy laws, though specific provisions vary.

In HyAfrica countries, natural hydrogen remains legally undefined. South Africa includes it informally under broad petroleum definitions, with the Petroleum Agency (PASA) issuing limited exploration licences. Morocco lacks formal legislation, although ONHYM has initiated exploratory permits. Mozambique’s laws also omit hydrogen, though the Mining and Petroleum frameworks could accommodate it. A similar situation is found in Togo, albeit the Ministry of Mines and Energy Resources, in the framework of HyAfrica has started a discussion on the possibilities. The country is developing a hydrogen strategy aligned with its energy transition goals.

Despite the absence of dedicated legal instruments, there is strong interest in natural hydrogen across all countries. The report recommends using existing legal frameworks as a starting point, while gradually building dedicated regulations. A stakeholder-driven approach and country-specific roadmaps are essential to support licensing, environmental oversight, and investment readiness in this emerging sector.

Keywords

Natural Hydrogen, regulatory framework, Morocco, South Africa, Mozambique, Togo.

1. Introduction

The aim of HyAfrica is to assess the resources of natural hydrogen in promising regions of four African countries (Morocco, Mozambique, South Africa, and Togo) and evaluate its socio-economic impact if deployed as an energy source for local communities.

Hydrogen is an attractive, clean, sustainable energy source primarily produced via industry. At present, most reviews on hydrogen focus on the preparation and storage of hydrogen, while the development and utilization of natural hydrogen, from a geologic origin, is expected not only to greatly reduce the hydrogen cost, but also giving it another role, as a clean primary energy source and not merely as an energy carrier to store energy from renewable sources. Natural hydrogen has been discovered in many geological environments, such as in oceanic spreading ridges, transform faults, passive margins, convergent margins, and intraplate settings. The primary sources of the hydrogen include alterations in Fe (II)-containing rocks, the radiolysis of water, degassed magma, and the reaction of water- and silica-containing rocks during the mechanical fracturing. Hydrogen can appear in free gas; it can be adsorbed or trapped in inclusions (Wang., et al., 2023). Currently, natural hydrogen exploration is in its formative stages. In Africa, it is anticipated that one of the drawbacks of the wide use of natural hydrogen is the lack of specific legislation associated with limited knowledge of the potential reserves, the dynamics associated with the regeneration of geogenic hydrogen, and its usage.

The WP4 aims to develop mechanisms in which natural H₂ can be incorporated in the national laws for exploration and production. Given that the subject is newly emerging in countries, legislation gaps are expected in terms of institutions responsible for promotion, licensing and even royalties associated in the H₂ exploitation. Specific objectives are: i) Legislation and regulation gap analysis on licensing the exploitation of H₂; ii) Development of roadmaps for H₂ exploration, exploitation and use.

1.1 Objectives

This report is part of WP4 of HyAfrica of which the main expected outcomes include:

- i. Integration of Natural hydrogen in the national energy laws – overview of the possibilities achieving these objectives implies benchmarking of some countries where Natural H₂ has been incorporated in the national legislation;
- ii. proposal for the inclusion of the H₂ in the legislation and,
- iii. agree with national stakeholder the most appropriate institution to host the H₂ legislation.

Task 4.2 of the HyAfrica project includes the development of customised strategies to potentially address the main regulatory gaps identified under Task 4.1 (see HyAfrica deliverable D4.1). Having identified the current status and gaps in the regulatory framework, the HyAfrica local teams, in close cooperation with the local

stakeholders' representatives, in this deliverable suggest alternatives and options to address the main challenges identified in the target countries.

The results of this task will lead the development process of a National Action Plan on the legislation of the H₂ exploration and exploitation define pathways for the assignment of responsibilities among the country peers on how to influence the decision-makers on the need for legislating natural hydrogen for its entire value chain.

1.2 Methodology

Each country was encouraged to propose the best ways for the inclusion of the natural hydrogen in the national legislation:

1. As a first step, a benchmark for the H₂ legislation is discussed, taking as examples Australia, France, Colombia and Poland;
2. A second step was to discuss, for each target country, the possible approaches for the inclusion of the H₂ in the national legislation
3. Finally, each local team would identify the correct institution for hosting the legislation of H₂ and who would be responsible for issuing licences and permits for exploration and production of H₂.

2. Benchmark for natural H₂ legislation

The benchmarking is based on the laws that encapsulate the natural H₂ in some countries such as Australia, France, Poland and Colombia.

Governments play an important role in sustaining and accelerating the transition to a low-carbon energy system by supporting the development and diffusion of new renewable energy technologies (Mazzucato and Semieniuk, 2017; UNEP, 2017). These efforts are at least partly motivated by a desire to contribute to mitigating climate change and other global environmental problems (European Commission, 2009).

2.1 South Australia

In South Australia, the Petroleum and Geothermal Energy Regulations 2013 revoked the Petroleum and Geothermal Energy Regulations 2000.

The new Petroleum and Geothermal Energy Regulations 2013, among other additions, made the following inclusion:

"(2) For the purposes of paragraph (f) of the definition of regulated substance in section 4(1) of the Act, the following are declared to be regulated substances to which the Act applies:

- (a) *hydrogen;*
- (b) *a hydrogen compound or other substance that is a by-product of the production of hydrogen”.*

This implies that all regulations under the Petroleum and Geothermal Energy Act 2020, now also applies to hydrogen and hydrogen compounds in terms of licensing for exploration, production, and pipelines and flow lines. This act also regulates the Environment Protection under the same act.

2.2 Colombia

In Colombia, “the Article 2 of Law 2294 of 2023 provides that the document called ‘Bases of the National Development Plan 2022-2026 Colombia World Power of Life’, together with its annexes, is an integral part of the National Development Plan (PND) and indicates that it is incorporated, as an annex, into the same law. In turn, the aforementioned document contains five changes, the fourth of these being called “*Productive transformation, internationalization and climate action*”, in whose catalyst C. “*Fair, safe, reliable and efficient energy transition*” contains a pillar focused on the energy transition, called “*2. Economic development based on energy efficiency, new energy sources and strategic minerals for the transition*”. Within this same framework, the national Government emphasises the duty to *advance in the use of Natural Hydrogen, associated with geological processes in the Earth's crust and found in its natural form as free gas in different environments.*

In accordance with the aforementioned precepts, and taking into account the technical and operational knowledge, that the Ministry of Mines and Energy has, the entity is empowered to regulate the methodology, establish the technical guidelines for the issuance of administrative acts that authorise the development of evaluation, exploration and exploitation activities of the resource, and determine the feasibility of developing Projects of National and Strategic Interest (Pines) on issues related to **Natural Hydrogen**.

“Article 5°. Definitions.

(...)

26. *Natural Hydrogen: It is hydrogen that is produced naturally, associated with geological processes in the Earth's crust and that is found in its natural form as free gas in different geological environments, whether in layers of the continental crust, in the oceanic crust, in volcanic gases, and in hydrothermal systems, such as in geysers, and is considered FNCER.”*

Article 1°. *Add articles 2.2.7.1.15, 2.2.7.1.16, 2.2.7.1.17, 2.2.7.1.18, 2.2.7.1.19, 2.2.7.1.20, 2.2.7.1.21, 2.2.7.1.22, 2.2.7.1.23 and 2.2.7.1.24 to Chapter 1 of Title VII, of Part 2 of Book 2, called “General conditions and guidelines on **hydrogen**” of Decree No. 1073 of 2015, as follows:*

“Article 2.2.7.1.15. *Implementation of **Natural Hydrogen** projects in the country.*

The Ministry of Mines and Energy, directly or through the entity designated for this purpose, shall determine the guidelines, conditions and technical requirements that must be met by the projects for carrying out evaluation studies of Natural Hydrogen and other gases or associated substances and their subsequent exploration and exploitation. Likewise, this Ministry, or the entity designated by it, shall be responsible for authorizing the interested parties, as well as for monitoring and controlling compliance with these conditions and technical requirements that are necessary to ensure high standards of quality and safety, specified in Colombian technical standards, or in the absence of these, the existing international technical standards on the matter shall apply.

*Paragraph 2°. The Ministry of Mines and Energy or the entity it designates, will issue the regulations referred to in this article, within twelve (12) months after the entry into force of these regulations, in which the rights, conditions and obligations for carrying out the activities of Evaluation Studies, Exploration and Exploitation of **Natural Hydrogen** and other associated gases or substances are established.*

Article 2.2.7.1.16.

*Definitions or the purposes of the provisions of this Chapter in relation to **Natural Hydrogen** and other associated gases or substances, without prejudice to other definitions established in the technical regulations issued by the Ministry of Mines and Energy, or the entity it designates, the following definitions shall be adopted:*

*Co-production of **Natural Hydrogen**: Exploitation of Natural Hydrogen in areas assigned for exploration and/or exploitation activities of hydrocarbons, minerals or geothermal energy.*

*Developer: Legal entity or energy communities that hold the Authorization to develop Evaluation, Exploration and/or Exploitation Studies of **Natural Hydrogen** and other gases or substances associated with it for the use of this resource.*

*Interested: Legal entity or energy communities that request Authorization from the Ministry of Mines and Energy, or from the entity it designates, for the development of **Natural Hydrogen** projects and other gases or substances associated with this resource in the national territory, whether it be the Authorization for Evaluation Studies, for Exploration and/or for Exploitation.*

*Mechanism: It is the administrative authorisation that contains the rights and obligations in favour of the Developer to carry out the activities of Evaluation, Exploration and/or Exploitation of **Natural Hydrogen** and other gases or associated substances in the national territory, a mechanism that may vary eventually according to the development and evolution of the sector in the country.*

*Other gases or substances associated with **Natural Hydrogen**: All those gases or substances that can be found stored naturally in reservoirs or that could be produced in conjunction with the exploitation of Natural Hydrogen.*

Article 2.2.7.1.17. Exclusiveness.

*The Developer who has obtained authorisation to carry out Evaluation Studies of **Natural Hydrogen** and other gases or substances associated with it, as well as the exploration and/ or exploitation of a certain area, will have exclusivity over other applicants while this authorisation is in force. This, without prejudice to the fact that, in the event of an express manifestation of the loss of interest by a Developer, the assigned area may be requested by a new interested party, in accordance with the provisions of the regulations issued by the Ministry of Mines and Energy or the entity it designates.*

Article 2.2.7.1.18. Environmental considerations.

*In accordance with the powers granted by Law 99 of 1993, Law 1715 of 2014 as amended by Law 2099 of 2021 and Decree No. 1076 of 2015 and the regulations that complement or add to it, the Developer must comply with all applicable environmental requirements, including obtaining the environmental license, permits, concessions, authorisations and other environmental procedures required to prevent, mitigate, correct or compensate for the duly identified environmental impacts and effects that may arise in the areas of Evaluation Studies, Exploration and/or Exploitation of **Natural Hydrogen** and other associated gases and substances.*

Article 2.2.7.1.19. Co-production.

*The Ministry of Mines and Energy, or the entity it designates, will regulate the special conditions it deems necessary for the co-production of **Natural Hydrogen** and other gases or substances associated with this resource in the areas and activities of exploration and/or exploitation of hydrocarbons, minerals or geothermal energy.*

Article 2.2.7.1.20. Coexistence.

*The Developer who has obtained authorization to carry out Evaluation, Exploration and/or Exploitation Studies of **Natural Hydrogen** and other gases or substances associated with it, must promote the coexistence of the projects in the event of overlap with another project in the mining and energy sector, in accordance with the provisions of current regulations.*

Article 2.2.7.1.21. Mechanism.

*The Ministry of Mines and Energy, or the entity it designates, may issue measures, guidelines and conditions to modify the mechanism for granting rights for the execution of **Natural Hydrogen** projects and other associated gases or substances in the country.*

*If the mechanism for granting rights for the execution of Evaluation, Exploration and Exploitation projects for **Natural Hydrogen** and other associated gases or substances is modified, in the case of Developers who hold rights under the administrative authorization mechanism, they will continue to execute their authorizations under the terms and conditions established in the respective administrative acts; this, without prejudice to the transition rules that the Ministry*

of Mines and Energy defines in technical matters in order to promote the protection of the environment, as well as the quality and safety of operations.

Article 2.2.7.1.22. Delivery of technical information.

*In development of the rights granted through the Mechanism for **Natural Hydrogen** projects by the Ministry of Mines and Energy, or whoever it designates, in accordance with the confidentiality of the information established in each specific case, the Developer must send to the Colombian Geological Service (SGC), the technical documentation that is determined, reporting this delivery to the Hydrocarbons Directorate of the Ministry of Mines and Energy, or to whomever it designates.*

Article 2.2.7.1.23. Promotion and Incentive of Natural Hydrogen Projects.

The national Government will implement instruments to promote and encourage the work of Evaluation Studies, Exploration, Exploitation and the use of Natural Hydrogen and other gases or substances associated with this renewable resource, without prejudice to what is applicable in accordance with the provisions of the framework in Law 1715 of 2014 amended and added by Laws 2099 of 2021 and 2294 of 2023, its other modifying and regulatory norms and the tax and other benefits described in Decree number 895 of 2022 regarding projects with non-conventional energy sources (FNCE) when applicable.

Article 2.2.7.1.24. Social participation.

*Without prejudice to compliance with the applicable regulations regarding citizen participation, the Developer must promote the implementation of community participation mechanisms in the area of influence of the project, regarding which the Ministry of Mines and Energy may establish, within the framework of the guidelines, conditions and requirements it issues for the implementation of Evaluation Studies, Exploration and Exploitation projects for **Natural Hydrogen** and other associated gases or substances, the social duties that the Developer must take into account in the exercise of the rights and obligations determined in the respective Authorization."*

2.3 France

In France, Order No. 02022-536 of April 13, 2022 modifying the mining model and the legal regimes falling under the mining code.

Article 3

Chapter I of Title I from book I is thus modified:

*1st Article L. 111-1 is supplemented by a paragraph worded as follows: "16th **Native hydrogen**";*

"Art. L. 114-3-2. –Under their own provisions, mining titles may be granted to one or more natural persons or legal entities. However, among these titles, exploitation titles may only be granted to legal entities".

2.4 Poland

Poland has recently amended its Geological and Mining Law (Act of 9 June 2011, as amended) to explicitly bring hydrogen within the scope of its hydrocarbon regulations. In late 2023, a new Article 2a was introduced, stating that all provisions relating to hydrocarbons “*apply to noble gases and to hydrogen*”. This effectively integrates *natural hydrogen* into the existing legal framework for oil and gas, even though the law does not use the term “natural hydrogen” explicitly. Hydrogen deposits are now legally treated as mineral resources of strategic importance: they are classified as mining property belonging to the State. Consequently, any exploration or extraction of hydrogen in Poland must follow the same concession and licensing requirements that apply to hydrocarbons.

In practice, a company seeking to explore or produce hydrogen will need to obtain a mining concession from the relevant authorities under the same procedures and oversight as for natural gas or oil. These amendments ensure that hydrogen – including naturally occurring hydrogen – is fully covered by Poland’s mining law framework, from exploration through to production and underground storage, aligning the country’s regulations with the emerging importance of hydrogen in the energy transition.

2.5 Summary

Table 1 summarises the benchmarking exercise for the natural hydrogen in France, Colombia, South Australia and Poland.

Table 1 - Summary of the legislation benchmarking for natural hydrogen

Country	Law or act	Natural hydrogen included	Framework	Other gases	Custodian Ministry	Licenses for H ₂ exploration
South Australia	Petroleum and Geothermal Energy Regulations 2013	yes	Hydrocarbons law	Yes	Petroleum and Geothermal Energy	Yes
Colombia	Law 2294 of 2023; DECREE 2235 OF 2023	Yes	Mining and Energy law	Yes	Mines and Energy	Yes
France	Order No. 02022-536 of April 13, 2022	Yes	Mining law	Yes	Ecological Transition	Yes
Poland	Mining Laws No. 163 of 2011	Indirectly	Mining law	Yes	Mines	No

The benchmark exercise on legal framework of France, Colombia, South Australia and Poland show that the choice of policy instruments depends on the identified

gaps presented in the Deliverable 4.1, as well as the precise goal of a policy and the scope of the natural hydrogen under study.

Therefore, it is important to determine the policy goal of the identified and respective requirements of usage because new emerging energy provides different opportunities, which can lead to different policy goals and changes to these goals over time. For the interpretation of the results, it is important to determine what the goal is.

Policy goals underpins the vision of the government with respect to renewable energy. These can be short- or long-term goals for renewable energies, i.e. the use of natural hydrogen for mini off-grids to resolve a specific problem in society by providing sustainable and renewable energy to rural communities. The policy goals, with respect to renewable energy, could be to help guarantee a stable energy supply and a reduction of fossil fuel dependency.

3. Status and options for the HyAfrica countries

3.1 Natural Hydrogen in the national laws

3.1.1 South Africa

In Deliverable 4.1, it was determined that, at this time, there is no legislation specifically addressing the exploration and exploitation of natural hydrogen in South Africa.

The Mineral and Petroleum Resources Development Act (MPRDA, Act No. 28, 2002), amended by the Minerals and Energy Laws Amendment Act 11 of 2005, the Gas Act (Act No. 48 of 2001), and the Upstream Petroleum Resources Development Act 23 of 2024 (UPRDA) does not specifically refer to natural hydrogen. However, the definitions for a **mineral**, a **combustible gas**, and **petroleum** in the three Acts, are wide enough to accommodate natural hydrogen (see Deliverable 4.1).

The Petroleum Agency South Africa (PASA) is the regulatory body for oil and gas exploration and production in South Africa under the auspices of the Mineral and Petroleum Resources Development Act, 2002. This agency is responsible for the regulation of petroleum exploration and all activities associated with production within the country, and acts as the custodian of the national database with respect to this data.

Although no regulatory body has taken responsibility for the licensing and regulation of natural hydrogen in South Africa, companies have been able to secure exploration licenses with PASA as part of exploration licenses for other petroleum products. No other legislation or regulatory frameworks are in place for natural hydrogen in South Africa.

The green hydrogen economy, on the other hand, forms a significant part of the country's drive towards achieving net-zero carbon emissions by 2050. South Africa's focus is predominantly on the development of legislation and strategies supporting the manufacturing and exploitation of a green hydrogen economy.

The Hydrogen Society Roadmap (HSRM, DSI, 2021) identified key sectors that can dramatically reduce their carbon footprint by incorporating green hydrogen in their energy structures. The key sectors include the heavy-duty transport sector, energy-intensive industries and the energy-generating sectors. This Roadmap also focus on manufacturing hydrogen-related solutions and products and the development of potential export markets for these technologies. Through extensive investigations and stakeholder engagements, the HSRM aims to utilise South Africa's natural and intellectual resources to become a leader in the global hydrogen market.

3.1.2 Morocco

To date, Morocco does not have specific legislation that directly addresses the exploration and exploitation of natural hydrogen. However, the current legal framework, particularly the Mining Law (Dahir n°1-15-76) and the Hydrocarbons Law (Law n°21-90 and its amendments), offers a foundation that could potentially accommodate natural hydrogen.

Under the Mining Code, the definition of “substances of mine” includes gases found in a natural state, but natural hydrogen is not explicitly listed. Similarly, the Hydrocarbons Law governs the exploration and exploitation of liquid and gaseous hydrocarbons but does not mention hydrogen, natural or otherwise. Nevertheless, these texts could, through interpretation or amendment, serve as a legal entry point for regulating natural hydrogen activities.

At the institutional level, ONHYM (Office National des Hydrocarbures et des Mines) is mandated by the State to manage exploration and development activities in the hydrocarbons sector only, while the mining sector falls under the responsibility of the Ministry of Energy Transition and Sustainable Development.

As part of its exploratory strategy, ONHYM has secured two large areas under exclusive permits dedicated to the assessment of natural hydrogen potential. These zones are currently the subject of three active partnerships with national and international stakeholders, aiming to evaluate the potential. These collaborations reflect growing interest in natural hydrogen as a potentially strategic and low-emission energy source.

Given the increasing strategic interest in clean energy resources and the promising preliminary indications of natural hydrogen occurrences, there is a recognized need for the Moroccan government to adopt a dedicated legal and institutional framework. Such a framework would define:

- The legal status of natural hydrogen (as a mineral, hydrocarbon, or new energy resource),
- Licensing procedures for exploration and exploitation,
- Environmental safeguards and regulatory oversight,
- Institutional responsibilities (e.g., whether ONHYM, the Ministry of Energy Transition, or another entity would serve as the regulatory authority),
- Fiscal regime (e.g., royalties, taxation).

From a legal and operational point of view, it appears more relevant to integrate natural hydrogen within the scope of Law 33-13 on mining activities, rather than under the Hydrocarbons Law. Unlike the latter, integrating natural hydrogen into the mining code would allow greater synergies with existing permitting procedures, environmental regulations, and institutional competencies already in place under the mining authority. It also reflects the renewable and geological character of natural hydrogen, and being carbon-free, so not at all a hydrocarbon.

From an investment perspective, the mining law is more attractive in terms of ownership structure and investor autonomy. Unlike the hydrocarbons regime, which automatically grants the Moroccan State (via ONHYM) a 25% carried interest in any

production project, the mining law does not impose any mandatory state participation in exploration or exploitation permits.

However, the hydrocarbons code offers superior fiscal incentives (IS exemptions, VAT recovery, customs exemptions) that do not exist under the mining law.

3.1.3 Mozambique

Mozambique does not have a specific legislation for natural hydrogen exploration and exploitation. Currently the Mining Law number. 20/14, of August 18 (Mining Law), emerges from the principles defined in the Policy and Strategy of the mineral resources, approved through Resolution number 89/13, of December 31. In an attempt to materialize the principles defined therein, the law number 20/14 includes provisions aiming at promoting the private investment through fiscal benefits and security of tenure of the mineral rights, local community benefits through allocation of a percentage of revenues generated from mining activity for the development of local communities, as a pre-stage towards revenue sharing with the local communities.

The main legislation relating to the exploration and development of the country's oil and natural gas includes, amongst others, the following key statutes:

- Constitution of the Republic of Mozambique;
- Law no. 21/2014, August 18 (Petroleum Law), as amended by Law no. 16/2022;
- Decree no. 34/2015, December 31 (Petroleum Law Regulation), as amended by Decree no. 48/2018, August 6 and Decree no. 34/2019, May 2.

The Ministry of Natural Resources ("MIREME") is responsible for directing and executing the governmental natural resource policies and for the supervision of the INP, created by the Council of Ministers under Decree no. 25/2004, August 20, the INP (National Petroleum Institute) being the regulatory authority responsible for the administration and promotion of Petroleum Operations.

Mozambican Government has established a few years ago an authority that is responsible for regulating, controlling and supervising the energy sector in Mozambique, i.e., the Energy Regulatory Authority ("Autoridade Reguladora de Energia" – "ARENE") through the approval of Law no. 11/2017, September 8 (the "Law").

The MIREME establishes the rules of negotiated access to the distribution network and the concessionaires should negotiate access rights with transparency, being barred from imposing any discriminatory conditions.

The Mozambican government has set itself the goal of placing the country among the leaders in hydrogen production in southern Africa by 2030, within the scope of the Energy Transition Strategy (ETS).

The first step set out in the so-called "hydrogen strategy" is to develop, later this year (2025), "a comprehensive plan for the development of the sector based on an

in-depth analysis and it will be necessary to decide on the scale of hydrogen production envisaged”.

The role that hydrogen will play in decarbonising the Mozambican economy will be defined, given its ability to enable transport and industrial solutions with lower emissions and lower costs.

Mozambique wants to establish objectives “regarding the production and consumption of hydrogen”, as well as the measures needed to achieve these goals, “including the development of hydrogen infrastructure”. The government also plans to “establish regional partnerships” with southern African countries “for a regional hydrogen economy, reducing the costs of developing hydrogen infrastructure and creating a broad market for hydrogen products and services.

3.1.4 Togo

In Togo, the laws in force on mining and hydrocarbons do not address natural hydrogen.

The mining code, initially established by Law No. 96-004 on the mining code of the Togolese Republic and revised in 2003 by Law No. 2003-12, governs the prospecting, exploration, exploitation, possession, processing, transportation, transformation, and trade of mineral substances and geothermal deposits on the territory of the Togolese Republic.

Hydrocarbons are governed separately by Law No. 99-003 on the Hydrocarbons Code of the Togolese Republic. This code regulates all petroleum operations, namely prospecting, exploration, research, exploitation, storage, refining, transportation, and marketing of petroleum and natural gas. It focuses on oil and gas: for example, it defines “hydrocarbons” primarily as crude oil in liquid or gaseous form. Pure hydrogen (H₂) is not a hydrocarbon by composition and therefore does not fall within the scope of these definitions.

It should be noted that apart from these two laws (the Mining Code and the Hydrocarbons Code), there are no other laws or specific policies that could relate to hydrogen in Togo. Natural hydrogen is a natural gas generated by geological processes but does not correspond exactly to the existing categories of minerals (solids) or hydrocarbons (fossil fuels).

Given this gap, the legal integration of natural hydrogen will require the modification of one of the existing legal frameworks. Countries that are pioneers in natural hydrogen tend to incorporate it into mining or petroleum laws, rather than creating entirely new legislation. Following this logic, Togo could choose to treat natural hydrogen as a georesource under the mining code or, alternatively, expand the scope of the hydrocarbon code to cover any natural gas resource. Each approach has implications. Integrating hydrogen into the mining regime would allow for the use of the Ministry of Mines and Energy Resources (MMRE) licensing procedures for resource exploration, but may require clarification that “mineral substances” include gas deposits.

On the other hand, the integration of hydrogen into the hydrocarbon sector would require a legal redefinition of the term “hydrocarbon” beyond its traditional meaning.

Regardless of the path chosen, an amendment is necessary to allow for the granting of licenses for the exploration of natural hydrogen. Based on international practices, a prudent recommendation is to integrate natural hydrogen into existing mining or petroleum laws (and their regulations) rather than waiting for stand-alone hydrogen legislation to be drafted. This ensures consistency with how other emerging producers treat natural hydrogen and allows Togo to capitalize on its existing legal infrastructure while the hydrogen sector is still in its infancy.

In summary, Togo should clarify in its mining or hydrocarbon code that natural hydrogen is a resource subject to exploration and exploitation permits/authorizations—for example, by amending legal definitions to include hydrogen. Such an update, combined with supporting regulations, would fill the legal void and align with the approach of jurisdictions that have already begun to regulate natural hydrogen as part of their extractive resources.

3.2 Institutional framework

3.2.1 South Africa

Given the lack of specific legislation for natural hydrogen exploration and exploitation, and the elevated hydrogen levels detected by soil surface measurements, it is the opinion of this consortium that regulatory bodies of South Africa should formulate more formal guidelines or legislation to address potential gaps.

Currently, the Petroleum Agency South Africa (PASA), which falls under the Department of Mineral Resources and Energy (DMRE), is ideally situated to, and is, issuing licenses for the exploration, presumably under the definition of petroleum:

*"any liquid, solid hydrocarbon **or combustible gas** existing in a natural condition in the earth's crust and includes any such liquid or solid hydrocarbon **or combustible gas**, which gas has in any manner been returned to such natural condition, but does not include coal, bituminous shale or other stratified deposits from which oil can be obtained by destructive distillation or gas arising from a marsh or other surface deposit"*

with an updated definition given in the Upstream Petroleum Resources Development Act 23 of 2024 (UPRDA) as

*"any liquid, solid hydrocarbon **or combustible gas** existing in a natural condition in the earth's crust, **and includes associated liquid or gas**, any liquid or solid hydrocarbon **or combustible gas**, but does not include coal, bituminous shale or other stratified deposits from which oil can be obtained by destructive distillation or gas arising from a marsh or other surface deposit"*

Since the identification, exploration and extraction of natural hydrogen would follow similar structures as the exploration of other natural gases, it is proposed that hydrogen be treated in the same way. This includes legislation regarding technical regulations, hydraulic fracturing, environmental impact assessments, and potential future international laws.

According to the Mineral and Petroleum Resources Development Act, all South Africa's mineral and petroleum resources are owned by the country under the custodianship of the Minister of Mineral Resources on behalf of the government. The Minister, therefore, has the authority to grant rights to explore for and extract resources, subject to the reimbursement to landowners for the potential loss of land use (Act 28 of 2002, Act 11 of 2005 and Act 49 of 2008). The licensing regime for petroleum-related resources includes a reconnaissance permit allowing for geological, geophysical and photo geological surveys, a technical cooperation permit that provides the exclusive rights to apply for and be granted an exploration right in a specific demarcated area, exploration rights to conduct exploration operations and activities in the area, and production rights (Norton Rose Fulbright, 2017).

Legislation regarding the storage, transportation and implementation of natural hydrogen into the larger planned hydrogen economy of South Africa can be combined with the work done by HySA and the Hydrogen Society Roadmap (HSRM, DSI, 2021).

The legislative focus in the HSRM incorporates several legislations and policy frameworks to support the development of the hydrogen economy are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2 - Legislation and Policies identified by the South African Hydrogen Society Roadmap (DSI, 2021)

Legislation and Policies		Short description
Energy and Climate Policies	White Paper on Energy Policy (1998)	A framework for regulating energy supply and demand, emphasising energy access, governance, and environmental management.
	White Paper on Renewable Energy Policy (2003)	Sets targets for renewable energy integration and mentions hydrogen as a potential future technology
	National Energy Act (2008):	Governs various aspects of energy supply and demand, including the development of integrated energy plans
	Integrated Resource Plan (IRP 2019)	Maps the future expansion of South Africa's electricity system, including renewable energy and mentions hydrogen's role in energy storage.
	National Climate Change Response White Paper (2011):	Outlines South Africa's commitment to reducing emissions via a peak, plateau, and decline trajectory.
	Carbon Tax Act (2019)	Taxes emissions from certain activities, including electricity generation, to incentivize low-carbon alternatives.
	Climate Change Bill (2021)	Provides a regulatory framework for managing emissions and allocating carbon budgets to activities generating greenhouse gases
Transport and Industrial Policies	Green Transport Strategy (2018):	Advocates for the deployment of hydrogen fuel-cell vehicles and other technologies to decarbonize the transport sector.

Legislation and Policies		Short description
	Beneficiation Strategy for Minerals Industry (2011)	Supports the development of technologies that benefit South Africa's mineral resources, including fuel-cell production.
	National Industrial Policy Framework (NIPF) and Industrial Policy Action Plan (IPAP)	Focus on green-industry investment and fuel-cell industry development
Building and Infrastructure Policies	Public Works and Infrastructure Green Building Policy (2018)	Promotes deploying green technologies, including hydrogen fuel cells, in public buildings
Hydrogen-Specific Policies	Hydrogen South Africa (HySA) Strategy (2007)	Focuses on research, development, and innovation in hydrogen and fuel-cell technologies
Environmental and Regulatory Frameworks	National Environmental Management: Air Quality Act (2004)	Regulates air quality and emissions, relevant for hydrogen production and use.
	Gas Act (2001)	Defines gas to include "hydrogen-rich gas," providing a basis for hydrogen distribution through piped-gas infrastructure

Natural and anthropogenic hydrogen have a role to play in the hydrogen economy for South Africa. While the green hydrogen community has made extensive strides towards legislation, it will be beneficial to the industry if both communities could achieve closer cooperation in developing a framework that addresses legislation from both sources.

3.2.2 Morocco

As Morocco begins to explore its potential in natural hydrogen, one of the key challenges lies in the absence of a specific legal and institutional framework to regulate and license this emerging resource. While there is growing interest and early activity in this field, a clear governance structure is still needed. Several options are available to the Moroccan authorities to structure regulation and oversight.

Option 1: Ministry of Energy Transition and Sustainable Development

A more conventional and balanced option would be to place regulatory authority under the Ministry of Energy Transition and Sustainable Development (METSD). This ministry is already responsible for implementing the Mining Law (Law 33-13), managing mining titles, and overseeing national energy policy.

In this model, METSD would define technical standards and regulatory requirements for natural hydrogen, issue exploration and production permits and coordinate with environmental and land-use authorities.

This setup would preserve a clear separation between policy and oversight (the Ministry) and operational promotion (ONHYM)—a model already used in the mining and energy sectors. It would also provide a more neutral and transparent framework for private investors.

Option 2: ONHYM

The second approach would be to assign regulatory responsibility to the Office National des Hydrocarbures et des Mines (ONHYM). ONHYM already plays a central role in managing exploration activities in the mining and hydrocarbons sectors. More importantly, it has taken the lead in initiating natural hydrogen exploration in Morocco, having secured two large prospective areas and established partnerships with national and international stakeholders.

Thanks to its technical capacity, experience in project management, and existing mandate in subsurface resource development, ONHYM is well positioned to take on a broader role in natural hydrogen. However, it currently operates as a state agency with both commercial and promotional functions—not as a regulator. For ONHYM to take on licensing and oversight responsibilities, its legal mandate would need to be expanded. This would also raise concerns about a potential conflict of interest between its roles as operator and regulator.

Option 3: Creating a New Hydrogen Regulatory Body

Morocco could also consider establishing a dedicated regulatory agency for hydrogen, covering both natural and green hydrogen. As hydrogen technologies evolve and begin to play a larger role in the country's energy transition.

Such an agency would develop integrated policies for the hydrogen sector and oversee licensing, safety, environmental monitoring, and investment promotion. However, creating a new agency would require significant time, resources, and legal reform. It is therefore more of a long-term option.

Option 4: dual-institutional model

In the short to medium term, the most practical approach would be a dual-institutional model. The Ministry of Energy Transition and Sustainable Development would serve as the main regulatory authority, under an amended legal framework (most likely the Mining Law) while ONHYM would continue to play a key role as a technical operator and project facilitator, supporting exploration, research, and public-private partnerships.

This division of roles would allow Morocco to build on existing institutional strengths while avoiding duplication or overlaps. As the sector grows, this model could evolve into a more integrated or dedicated regulatory structure, aligned with the strategic importance of hydrogen in Morocco's future energy mix.

3.2.3 Mozambique

The country is actively working on incorporating hydrogen into its energy strategy, aiming to become a regional leader in green hydrogen production. While specific legislation focused solely on hydrogen is still under development, the country is leveraging its existing energy framework and policies to pave the way for a hydrogen economy. This includes integrating hydrogen production into its broader Energy Transition Strategy and developing infrastructure for production, storage, and transportation.

The country is developing a comprehensive plan for the sector, including an in-depth analysis to determine the scale of hydrogen production and its main applications.

The government, through the Energy Regulatory Authority (ARENE), has announced that it is developing a specific legal framework to regulate autonomous renewable energy systems, such as off-grid systems and mini-grids.

Promoting a just energy transition, with a focus on the most vulnerable communities

The country is strengthening its commitment to the energy transition through an ambitious strategy that combines carbon emission reduction with the promotion of sustainable development. Thus, the time is right for widening the renewable matrix by inclusion of natural hydrogen.

Figure 1 - The key players in the natural Hydrogen legislation (DNGM: National Directorate of Geology and Mines; INP: National Petroleum Institute; ARENE: Energy Regulatory Authority; AMER: Mozambican Association of Renewable Energies)

3.2.3.1 Legislation options

In Mozambique there are at least three different options for incorporating the natural hydrogen.

Option one the natural hydrogen to be incorporated in the Mining Law, which is under review

MIREME is responsible for directing and implementing policies in the context of geological research, the inventory of and exploration for mineral resources including coal and hydrocarbons. In achieving these objectives, this Ministry, among other entities, is responsible for inventorying underground resources in national territory and in the exclusive economic zone (EEZ), promoting and controlling prospecting and geological exploration activities and the rational use of mineral resources.

The National Directorate of Geology and Mines (DNGM) of Mozambique serves as a pivotal institution in the realm of geological research and resource management within the country. Established to oversee the exploration and sustainable management of Mozambique's geological resources, this directorate plays a crucial

role in the advancement of geological sciences and the promotion of responsible mining practices.

The DNGM is dedicated to enhancing the understanding of Mozambique's geological framework, which is characterized by a diverse array of mineral resources and complex geological formations. Through its research initiatives, the DNGM contributes to the knowledge base surrounding the Pan-African geological evolution, particularly in northeastern Mozambique.

In addition to its research functions, the DNGM is involved in policy formulation and implementation related to geological exploration and environmental management. By fostering collaboration with local and international partners, the institution aims to promote best practices in geology and mining, ensuring that Mozambique's natural resources are utilized effectively and sustainably for the benefit of its people.

Considering that natural hydrogen is a natural resource, it could be also well placed at MIREME and regulated by the DNGM.

Option two, the natural hydrogen to be incorporated in the Petroleum Law which, is under review.

Considering that the Petroleum Law well establishes the legal framework for the hydrocarbons (petroleum and natural gas), and the fact that the INP is the regulatory entity responsible for administration and promotion of oil and natural gas operations.

The INP is responsible, among other duties, for the following:

- Regulation and auditing of oil and gas exploration, production and transport activity as well as ensuring policies for development and standards related to oil operations;
- Preservation of the public interest and the environment by establishing the required technical, commercial and environmental conditions, promoting the adoption of practices that encourage the efficient use of resources and the existence of quality standards that correspond to the service and protection of the environment; and
- Organization, maintenance and consolidation of the accuracy of technical data and information related to the activities of the oil industry, national oil reserves and the information produced.

This option would be more consistent with Mozambican legal framework where natural hydrogen would be regulated following the long-established path for the natural gas and it would benefit from the experience accumulated in this sector.

Option three, the natural hydrogen to be incorporated in the strategy for renewable energy resources matrix.

In regulating the natural hydrogen, it should be mindful of the fundamental realities of the Mozambican economy and energy sector. Mozambique is a poor country, with limited infrastructure and a large unskilled workforce and which, nevertheless, appears to be on the verge of becoming a major world player in the energy markets due to the significant discoveries of natural gas resources in the country. Lacking the internal capabilities to exploit these resources or an internal market for natural gas and natural hydrogen, the country continues to rely on outside developers to explore and produce for export.

While these gas discoveries are an additional economic windfall for Mozambique, they present serious challenges to the GoM in the broader political economy. These challenges lay in how to encourage development of the resources in a way that brings the greatest benefit to Mozambique.

The integration of natural hydrogen into the global energy sector strategy would bring multiple benefits. One would be to continue promoting the development of export-centered LNG projects while targeting the revenues for the development of the natural hydrogen systems. This would promote energy transition, with a focus on the most vulnerable communities.

All three options are valid and the key players need to agree on combined efforts and place natural hydrogen where most benefits can be generated for the country.

3.2.4 Togo

Togo's institutional landscape for mining and energy is anchored in the Ministry of Mines and Energy Resources. This ministry is the main government body responsible for overseeing the exploration and management of mineral and hydrocarbon resources, and it also supervises all natural hydrogen projects. The ministry (through its mining, geology, and hydrocarbon departments) is responsible for issuing exploration and production permits, monitoring compliance, and enforcing sector regulations.

At the same time, the National Environmental Management Agency (ANGE) is a public institution under the supervision of the Ministry of Environment and Forest Resources and supports national environmental policy. It plays a crucial role in environmental monitoring. ANGE ensures that mining or drilling projects, and by extension any future hydrogen exploration, undergo appropriate environmental impact assessments (EIAs) and comply with environmental protection standards.

Togo is also a member of the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative (EITI). The MMRE implements the principles or requirements of the EITI to promote transparency and accountability in the management of extractive revenues. This suggests that any exploitation of natural hydrogen would also be subject to transparency and environmental review by these institutions.

To effectively regulate and promote natural hydrogen, Togo should designate a lead institution while leveraging the strengths of other countries through coordination. The MMRE is responsible for implementing mining regulations and overseeing Togo's energy policy, and remains the guarantor of natural hydrogen regulation. It has two options for structuring natural hydrogen regulation.

- ✓ The first option is to entrust the regulation of white hydrogen at the General Direction of Mines and Geology (DGMG) by incorporating it into the mining code, which is currently under review.

The DGMG is an entity of the MMRE responsible for implementing policies in the mining sector, managing the state's mining domain, and ensuring the optimal exploitation of Togo's underground resources through the application of the mining code, controlling prospecting programs, and enforcing regulations for classified establishments.

As natural hydrogen is a natural resource, its introduction into the mining code will position Togo as a key player in the decarbonization of the mining sector and will attract investors and benefit from the DGMG's accumulated experience in implementing mining policy and coordinating with the institutions responsible for environmental management.

- ✓ The second option is to entrust it to the Hydrocarbons Directorate (DH) by incorporating it into the hydrocarbons code, which is also currently being reviewed.

The DH is also an entity of the MMRE whose mission is to execute and control programs for the exploration, development, production, refining, storage, distribution, and marketing of hydrocarbons; to manage and ensure optimal utilization of resources through the application of the Hydrocarbons Code; - monitor establishments classified as unhealthy and inconvenient from a health and environmental perspective in the state's hydrocarbon sector.

This second option would be more consistent if we considered natural gas for white hydrogen, but the exploration and production section of DH has been inactive since its creation due to a lack of manpower, internal capacity, and foreign investors to explore hydrocarbon and natural gas resources. The incorporation of natural hydrogen into this Directorate will be a major challenge.

This configuration between the MMRE and the DGMG or DH would maintain a clear separation between policy and supervision (the ministry) and operational management (DGMG or DH), with the possibility of evolving the framework by creating a division or authority dedicated to hydrogen once exploration results and market developments justify a more specialized regime. It would also offer a more neutral and transparent framework for private investors.

4. Conclusions

This deliverable 4.2 represents the benchmarking of the natural hydrogen legislations in several countries around the world, and relates to the HyAfrica Project by describing the regulatory status of each target country, and discusses suggestion on options for institutional framework. It is clear from the study that all target countries lack specific legislation for natural hydrogen. Regardless of lack of legislations, all countries are aware of the need for legislating the natural hydrogen in order to allow a regulatory environment for licencing, exploration and development of natural hydrogen.

These findings should be interpreted with caution given the nature of this study, associated with lack of regional references, but they encourage future studies to look at natural hydrogen in the context of the current energy transition and net zero by 2050. It will be important to devise holistic approaches in the target countries by integrating all relevant stakeholders for the design of natural hydrogen legislation, considering the specificity of the subsector in terms of production technologies, storage and transportation to the key markets.

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